

D3.3 – Pan-European Workshop on Edge AI technological trends and developments

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Reviewer(s)	Ovidiu Vermesan and Mohamed Selim

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
IoT	Internet of Things
NoE	Network of Excellence.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.3 (Pan-European Workshop on Edge AI technological trends and developments) is an outcome of task T3.2 (Edge AI technologies trends across the AI domains and industries) in work package WP3 (European Strategic Agenda and Road Mapping for Edge AI Research and Innovation) of the dAIEDGE project. The actual deliverable is the workshop entitled “Charting the Future of Edge AI”, which took place on January 21st, 2025, during the HiPEAC 2025 conference in Barcelona, Spain. This document is a short summary of the successful event.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background and rationale

Deliverable D3.3 (Pan-European Workshop on Edge AI technological trends and developments) is an outcome of task T3.2 (Edge AI technologies trends across the AI domains and industries) in work package WP3 (European Strategic Agenda and Road Mapping for Edge AI Research and Innovation) of the dAIEDGE project. The actual deliverable is the workshop entitled “Charting the Future of Edge AI”, which took place on January 21st, 2025, during the HiPEAC 2025 conference in Barcelona, Spain. This document is a short summary of the successful event.

This deliverable D3.3 (Pan-European Workshop on Edge AI technological trends and developments) is an outcome of task T3.2 (Edge AI technologies trends across the AI domains and industries) in work package WP3 (European Strategic Agenda and Road Mapping for Edge AI Research and Innovation).

This document summarises the workshop entitled “Charting the Future of Edge AI”, which took place on January 21st, 2025, during the HiPEAC 2025 conference in Barcelona, Spain. The workshop was organised by dAIEDGE¹ in collaboration with the Chips JU EdgeAI² project as one of the workshops of the HiPEAC conference that took place in Barcelona from January 20th to 22nd, 2025.

The workshop "Charting the Future of Edge AI: Functional and Non-Functional Requirements in the Age of Generative AI" workshop served as a dynamic platform for stakeholders to share their experiences, exchange ideas, and collaborate on shaping the future of edge AI technologies. Through a mix of expert presentations and engaging panel discussions, participants explored emerging research, shared best practices, and identified key trends that will shape the next generation of edge AI systems.

2. Charting the Future of Edge AI Workshop

Edge AI technologies represent a significant shift in artificial intelligence, integrating edge computing and the Internet of Things (IoT) to enable decentralized processing. Unlike traditional cloud-based AI systems that rely on centralized servers, edge AI moves computation closer to the data source, reducing latency and improving efficiency. This approach is particularly advantageous in applications that require real-time or near-real-time decision-making, such as industrial automation, healthcare, smart cities, autonomous vehicles, and interactive digital experiences.

As generative AI continues to evolve, unlocking novel possibilities across diverse domains, its convergence with edge computing is becoming increasingly crucial. The ability to deploy generative AI at the edge can enhance responsiveness, reduce reliance on cloud resources, and address

¹ dAIEDGE website: <https://daiedge.eu/>

² EdgeAI website: <https://edge-ai-tech.eu/>

challenges related to data privacy and security. Given this backdrop, the "Charting the Future of Edge AI" workshop brought together leading experts, researchers, and industry stakeholders to discuss essential aspects of edge AI deployment, focusing on both functional and non-functional requirements. The event facilitated knowledge exchange on cutting-edge advancements, critical challenges, industry best practices, and strategic insights necessary to develop robust, efficient, and scalable edge AI solutions in the era of generative AI.

2.1. Attendance and Organization

A total of 119 attendees from 77 institutions across 23 countries registered for the event, reflecting the growing interest and importance of edge AI research and development. The workshop took place on January 21, 2025, at the HiPEAC Conference in Barcelona, Spain. It was organized by the dAIEDGE project in collaboration with the Chips JU EdgeAI project, bringing together leading voices in academia and industry to discuss the evolving landscape of edge AI.

2.2. Key Discussion Topics

The workshop delved into various aspects of edge AI system design, emphasizing both functional and non-functional requirements necessary for optimal deployment.

- **Functional Requirements:** A major focus of the workshop was identifying the essential functionalities required for deploying AI models at the edge. Key aspects included ensuring seamless real-time data processing, enabling rapid decision-making capabilities, and optimizing AI inference efficiency. Discussions covered hardware and software design considerations, including processing power, memory constraints, and energy efficiency, which are critical for ensuring the smooth operation of AI at the edge.
- **Non-Functional Requirements:** Beyond core functionalities, the workshop also highlighted the importance of system-wide quality attributes. Topics covered aspects such as dependability, robustness, reliability, security, and availability. Additionally, discussions explored explainability and interpretability in edge AI systems, addressing how AI-driven decisions can be made transparent and trustworthy. Scalability and adaptability were also examined, particularly regarding how edge AI systems can evolve to accommodate diverse workloads and deployment scenarios across various industries.

By approaching these challenges through system engineering principles, participants gained deeper insights into designing and implementing effective and responsible edge AI solutions. The discussions helped frame a cross-disciplinary perspective on enhancing edge AI capabilities to meet the demands of generative AI applications.

2.3. Agenda and sessions

The workshop featured a series of insightful presentations that covered a wide range of topics related to edge AI, including its functional and non-functional aspects, emerging challenges, and future opportunities (Figure 1). The sessions included:

- **Edge AI Systems Functional and Non-Functional Requirements Engineering. Generative AI Future Trends and Concepts** – Ovidiu Vermesan, SINTEF, Norway
- **Generative AI at the Edge for the Metaverse** – Alain Pagani, DFKI, Germany
- **Challenges, Goals, and Trends for Smart Edge Agents** – Miguel de Prado, VERSES, Switzerland
- **A Touch-free Gesture Recognition System Powered by Edge AI** – Yves Piguet, CSEM, Switzerland
- **Panel Discussion: Edge AI Technology** – Participants: Nuria Pazos, HES-SO, Switzerland, Miguel de Prado, VERSES, Switzerland, Yves Piguet, CSEM, Switzerland, Moderator: Alain Pagani, DFKI, Germany
- **Low-Power Near-Sensor Intelligence: Advancing Micro-Edge Computing Beyond CNNs** – Paolo Meloni, University of Cagliari, Italy
- **Edge AI for Computer Vision: Challenges, Technological Advancements, and Future Trends** – Mhd Rashed Al Koutany, DFKI, Germany
- **SECDA-LLM: Designing Efficient LLM Accelerators for Edge Devices** – Jose Cano Reyes, University of Glasgow, UK
- Edge AI Future Trends and Strategic Research Agenda
- **A Versatile and Secure AI Platform with Reconfigurable RISC-V Based Parallel Processing** – Iakovos Mavroidis, Technical University of Crete, Greece
- **Edge AI Research Topics and Future Trends – Panel and open discussion** – Moderators: Ovidiu Vermesan, SINTEF, Norway and Alain Pagani, DFKI, Germany

Each session provided valuable insights into key technical and strategic aspects of edge AI, equipping participants with a deeper understanding of the field's current state and future trajectory.

Charting the Future of Edge AI
Functional and Non-Functional Requirements in the Age of Generative AI
Workshop

EDGE **Conference**

10:00 - 11:00 Session 1: Edge AI Functional and Non-functional Requirements in the Generative AI Era.

- Edge AI Systems Functional and Non-Functional Requirements Engineering. Generative AI Future Trends and Concepts, *Ovidiu Vermesan, SINTEF, Norway*
- Generative AI at the Edge for the Metaverse, *Alain Pagani, DFKI GmbH, Germany*

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee/Tee Break

11:30 - 13:00 Session 2: Technology Developments

- Challenges, Goals, and Trends for Smart Edge Agents, *Miguel de Prado, Verses, Switzerland*
- A Touch-free Gesture Recognition System Powered by Edge AI, *Yves Piguat, CSEM, Switzerland*

12:30 - 13:00 Panel discussion (Moderator: *Alain Pagani, DFKI GmbH, Germany*)

13:00 - 14:00 Buffet Lunch

14:00 - 15:30 Session 3: Application Developments

- Low-Power Near-Sensor Intelligence: Advancing Micro-Edge Computing Beyond CNNs., *Paolo Meloni, University of Cagliari, Italy*
- Edge AI For Computer Vision: Challenges, Technological Advancements, and Future Trends, *Mhd Rashed Al Koutayni, DFKI GmbH, Germany*
- SECD-LLM: Designing Efficient LLM Accelerators for Edge Devices, *Jose Cano Reyes, University of Glasgow, UK*

15:30 - 16:00 Coffee/Tee Break

16:00 - 17:00 Session 4: Edge AI Future Trends and Strategic Research Agenda

- Edge AI research topics and future trends

16:30 - 17:10 Panel discussion (Moderators: *Ovidiu Vermesan, SINTEF, Norway and Alain Pagani, DFKI GmbH, Germany*)

17:10 - 17:30 Future steps open discussion

17:30 End

Figure 1 – The agenda for the event.

2.4. Summary of the event

The workshop gathered numerous experts in the field of Edge AI to discuss the future trends and developments in the field. Researchers from various institutions such as University of Cagliari, University of Crete, University of Applied Sciences HES-SO, University of Glasgow, CSEM, VERSES, SINTEF and DFKI. The moderators were the project coordinators Alain Pagani (DFKI³) representing the dAIEDGE project and Ovidiu Vermesan (SINTEF⁴) representing the EdgeAI project.

Figure 2: Organisers Alain Pagani (DFKI) and Ovidiu Vermesan (SINTEF), and panelists of the first panel session Nuria Pazos (HES-SO), Miguel de Prado (VERSOS) and Yves Piquet (CSEM)

The workshop opened with a presentation of the dAIEDGE WP3 Leader Ovidiu Vermesan (SINTEF), who presented the goals of the workshop, important trends and relevant concepts. The dAIEDGE project coordinator, Alain Pagani (DFKI), presented the trend of Virtual Worlds and Metaverse, in which Edge AI will have an important role in the perception based on local sensors.

The following participants introduced important directions and applications of edge AI such as smart agents, wearables, computer vision, large language models.

The first panel session collected experts' views on the state of Edge AI and its foreseeable evolution. Opportunities and challenges have been discussed such as energy efficiency, privacy and security aspects.

³ DFKI website: <https://av.dfki.de/>

⁴ SINTEF website: <https://www.sintef.no/en/>

Figure 3: Speakers of the workshop Paolo Meloni (Uni Cagliari), Jose Cano (University of Glasgow), Nuria Pazos (HES-SO), Mhd Rashed Al Koutany (DFKI)

In the closing session, a discussion round has been conducted by Ovidius Vermesan, collecting key insights from the workshop participants around three main questions:

- What are the future trends in Edge AI
- What are the upcoming challenges in Edge AI
- What are the upcoming applications in Edge AI

A summary of the expressed views is provided below:

- An important goal is to lower the barrier between experimentation and the design of neural network architectures, particularly for Edge AI devices using hardware-in-the-loop approaches. By streamlining the design process and minimizing delays in the loop, we can accelerate development and reduce the time from design to experimentation. This approach is particularly relevant for applications such as wearables, where Edge AI extends the capabilities of IoT devices.
- There is a necessity to bridge the gap between laboratory research and real-world applications
- Explainability in EdgeAI is important: we need to get output from the AI systems that are meaningful. The explainability component should not affect the model performance, but should be implemented with specific visualization of the outputs.
- Various subtopics have very different maturity levels. While vision processing is highly mature, we need to advance human-computer interfaces through technologies like head tracking. Applications could be enabling a comprehensive view of patients in the healthcare sector.

- Development of wearable technology such as Augmented Reality glasses will push the need for efficient Edge AI components. In a foreseeable future, humans will be equipped with many sensors requiring EdgeAI capabilities
- Current research is more focused on accelerators, but the deployment phase is currently neglected and will become a challenge. Accelerator development should incorporate tutorial to deploy various models directly in the accelerators. There is a need for a system on a module that integrate sensor acceleration.
- While hardware acceleration currently tries to be inspired by biology (e.g. by imitating the human brain with spiking neural networks), the energy consumption is currently far from the performance of the human brain. There is a need to pursue research on the hardware side to develop bio-inspired hardware.
- There is a need to interoperability, covering hardware, software, data and models
- Development of Edge AI should be more application-oriented, with more emphasis on standardization for data acquisition
- Models are tested on middle-size benchmarks, but they are still difficult to scale up. We need more scalability on the use of data, on training with specific data and on data models.
- While current research focus a lot on accelerating machine learning (such as deep learning), the algorithms developed on edge must not be necessarily complex. Simpler algorithms are more resource efficient and can be useful in many applications
- The community should not only focus on the best performance on a few benchmarks, but also on how to offer the tolls and environment to facilitate the work with software and hardware. There is a need of high-level abstraction in edge AI.
- A future emerging topic in edge AI is collective intelligence using swarms of simple agents. We need to develop tools to use and optimize swarm intelligence
- While research progress and technology advances are impressive, research development is sometimes missing a clear focus on the actual constraints. We need tools to clarify the constraints, since a given solution cannot be the best solution for all devices. Unfortunately, there are currently no standard protocol to measure this adherence to constraints.
- Edge AI as a topic needs a better organization to avoid communication gaps between the subcommunities
- Chipllets and RISC-V are important emerging concepts that should be followed
- Heterogeneity of devices is a problem and requires standardized protocols. This could be done by defining operational domains, with clearly defined domain boundaries in which the devices can operate.
- Foundational models are emerging in AI, but still need to be properly addressed in Edge AI. We miss foundational models for specific sensors (vision, signal processing). The emergence of foundational pre-trained models in Edge AI would reduce the amount of data needed for fine-tuning specific subdomains.
- EdgeAI does not necessarily mean more complexity. It can and should be used for simpler applications such as IoT (very small data, simple application)

- A technological trend to follow is the use of large language models (LLMs) in a downscaled version (small LM).
- Generally, more maturity in the subcomponents of Edge AI (hardware, software, models, data) is required, since a single company or entity cannot have all the necessary skills to address optimally the underlying issues. Interoperability should be improved, since testing solutions from different providers is not easy today. Tools, hardware and the ecosystem should be more mature.
- While human-in-the-loop is today an important axis of research, we should also consider machine-machine communication so AI systems can use EdgeAI in a simple way.
- Mobile phones applications is a trend that will certainly continue (e.g. LLM on a mobile phone with in-memory processing)
- While consumer electronics is on focus today, industrial use cases should be considered to allow for technology development for specific industrial scenarios. This would allow for faster development. Consumer market can be reached in a second phase
- An important aspect which is currently missing in edge AI is the education of future researchers and developers. Edge AI is a topic that requires many different skills and the educational system should be prepared to educate students for edge AI.

2.5. Dissemination

The information about the event was published on the project websites under dAIEDGE news⁵ and EdgeAI events⁶ as illustrated in Figure 4.

⁵ dAIEDGE news: <https://daiedge.eu/news/three-days-innovation-and-technology-conclude-hipeac-2025>

⁶ EdgeAI events: <https://edge-ai-tech.eu/charting-the-future-of-edge-ai-workshop/>

Figure 4 - Reported under News and Events at the dAIEDGE and EdgeAI projects websites.

2.6. Next steps

This workshop is the continuation of a series of workshops organized in the frame of the WP3 of dAIEDGE with the aim to collect expert views to prepare the future of Edge AI in Europe. They serve as a opportunity to inform stakeholders of the efforts to prepare the future of Edge AI and contributes to aligning the terminologies used and categorization of the upcoming challenges. This is an important step towards preparing the roadmap and the edge AI strategic research agenda.

A paper on Edge AI technological trends and developments is in preparation (deliverable D3.4) and will be published in August 2025. In parallel, dAIEDGE will organise a dedicated workshop to discuss in depth the requirements for a strategic research agenda. The paper and the upcoming workshop will be an important step to prepare the Strategic Research Agenda for Edge AI, as main output of the WP 3 in the project dAIEDGE.

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